

TEACHING VOCABULARY TO STUDENTS WITH LEARNING DIFFICULTIES

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Annotation: In this thesis I took down the theme Teaching vocabulary to students with learning difficulties. I highlighted some challenges during teaching vocabulary to slow-learners.

Key words: teaching vocabulary, context, learning disability, dyslexic, strengths, problems, weaknesses, techniques

“The first exercises in the new material should be very easy; not until later should more difficult material be introduced and practiced.”

Learning vocabulary is a basic constituent of learning a language. The more words we know, the better we understand what we read and listen to. Our vocabulary knowledge also reflects how well we can express ourselves in speaking and writing. Because of the importance of vocabulary to the four macro skills as well as to our study and life, much attention has been paid and many studies have been conducted to investigate effective vocabulary learning strategies.¹

Why do some students suffer from learning vocabulary? How much time do they spend on learning by heart? These are the most frequent questions I have been thinking about. I have discussed them with many pupils, teachers and parents. Reactions and opinions were, of course, different. Frequent complain of many teachers is that it is extremely difficult to teach children that seem to lack the basic talent for learning languages. Therefore I would like to refer to the possibilities which teaching a foreign language to students with learning difficulties.

According to an article published by The International Dyslexia Association “² ... many students have difficulties learning a new language system. This does not mean that they are dyslexic or that they have a learning disability. Just as there are some

students who have particular strengths in math, science, or any other discipline, some students have particular strengths in learning languages.”

The teacher should be aware of this and whenever they realize the students' weaknesses (difficulties) be able to provide appropriate pedagogical help (teaching method) as otherwise these difficulties start to pile up and later on they can have a negative influence on learners. As a result, this failure causes them stress and, they lose their self-confidence and self-esteem. Thus, the teacher should know how to prevent students with these difficulties from experiencing problems and show them a way to manage to accommodate the language.

From a student's perspective, it becomes difficult to simply memorize words and terms that they have no prior connections to. We can use activities and games of teaching vocabulary during our lessons. Unfortunately, many students struggle to remember what the vocabulary words mean. To help students learn the definitions we can try these classroom vocabulary games with our students pair up and create a checkerboard out of paper. Then, they should write a vocabulary word in each square. As the student play the game, they need to provide the correct definition of the word in the square. They could also make up a sentence using the word. If the student can do it, they get to claim that square.

In the thesis Andrea HOLEŠINSKÁ² cited “The latter mentioned method uses different objects (instruments) in the classroom to create connections between “abstract” vocabulary and “real” things. Thus these techniques help to build learners background knowledge with using their senses to learn about a given subject.

Among the presentation techniques belong:

- Realia - real objects are used as examples
- Pictures - explaining the meaning of vocabulary items through pictures
- Mime, action and gesture – this technique uses a human body to express for example grammatical points, verbs or tenses
- Contrast - presenting the meaning of a certain word by contrasting it with the opposite one

- Enumeration - general and specific meaning of words
- Explanation - giving a definition
- Translation – the easiest technique but not productive

An important part of presentation techniques (introducing new words) is pronunciation

which should not be underestimated.”

All in all, vocabulary plays an essential role in learning any language. It is very difficult to learn another language without learning the words, without knowing their meaning. Taking a student's point of view - the teacher should adjust lesson plans to accommodate any problems students encounter as they learn new words. Show them how to take a word they have never heard of before, sound it out, and show its use in a sentence or two. They will pick up on its meaning through the sentences. Simple and effective vocabulary strategies help our students build an magnificent vocabulary.

Used literature:

1 Patel N (2017) “Effective Vocabulary Instruction: Five Best Practices for Teachers”

2 Ganshow, Leonore, and Schneider, Elke. “At-risk students and the study of a foreign language in school.” 2005.

3 Andrea HOLEŠINSKÁ “Teaching English as a foreign language to students with learning difficulties” 2006